

Caddo

also known as “Hasí:nay”

By Ryan Hechler, Tulane University / SWCA Environmental Consultants

Entry tags: Religious Group, Native American (North American) Religions, Language, Caddoan, Caddo

The Caddo are archaeologically renowned for their monumental ritual spaces, spiritually charged artwork, and unique ritual traditions. Caddoan culture was archaeologically distinct from the larger Pre-Contact Mississippian culture traditions. Important Caddo communities and monumental centers were found throughout eastern Texas (e.g., Caddoan Mounds site), northwestern Louisiana (e.g., Gahagan Mounds site), western Arkansas (e.g., Battle Mound site), eastern Oklahoma (e.g., Spiro Mounds site), and southwestern Missouri. As a result of generations of colonialism and displacement, the Caddo Nation resides in Oklahoma, outside and west of their ancestral territory.

Date Range: 800 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Ancestral Caddo Territory

Region tags: North America, United States of America, U.S. Southeast

The ancestral territory of the Caddo: eastern Texas, northwestern Louisiana, western Arkansas, eastern Oklahoma, and southwestern Missouri. The modern Caddo Nation resides in Binger, Oklahoma, west of their ancestral territory.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

ID: 4651

- Source 1: Carter, Cecile. *Caddo Indians: Where We Come From*. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 2001.
- Source 2: LaVere, David. *The Caddo Chiefdoms: Caddo Economics and Politics, 700-1835*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1998.
- Source 3: Perttula, Timothy. *The Caddo Nation: Archaeological and Ethnohistoric Perspectives*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1997.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

ID:
4652

– Source 1 URL: <https://mycaddonation.com/history-1>

– Source 1 Description: Caddo Nation. "Caddo Nation Website: Who We Are," 2023.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.nps.gov/elte/learn/historyculture/caddo-early-history.htm>

– Source 2 Description: National Park Service. "NPS Website: Early Caddo History - El Camino Real de Los Tejas," 2025.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

ID: 4653

– Source 1 URL:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Delisle_Carte_de_la_Louisiane_et_du_cours_du_Mississippi_1718_UTA.jpg

– Source 1 Description: "Carte de la Louisiane et du cours du Mississippi" by Guillaume Delisle, 1718

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

ID: 4654

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

ID: 4655

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

ID: 4660

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

ID: 4661

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

ID: 4662

– No

↳ Assigned by class: ID: 4663
– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age: ID: 4664
– Yes

↳ Assigned by gender: ID: 4665
– Yes

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual: ID: 4666
– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor: ID: 4667
– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members: ID: 4668
– No

Does the religion have official political support ID: 4676
– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group: ID: 4684
– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished: ID: 4685
– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified: ID: 4686
– Yes

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical): ID: 4699

– Estimated population, numeric: 6000

Notes: 6000 members of the modern Caddo Nation, the historic Caddo Confederation was substantially more prior the physical and biological impacts of European Colonialism.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical): ID: 4700

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Modern Caddo are largely members of various sects of Christianity.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures: ID:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India). ID: 4729

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present: ID: 4745

– Yes

Notes: The Caddo were renowned for large-scale monumental earthen mounds to house religious and political structures.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture: ID: 4752

– Yes

Tombs: ID: 4753

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries: ID: 4754

– Yes

↳ Temples: ID: 4755

– Yes

↳ Altars: ID: 4756

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers: ID: 4757

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]: ID: 4758

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture: ID: 4759

– No

Is iconography present: ID: 4764

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]: ID: 4765

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography: ID: 4766

– Yes

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not): ID: 4767
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic): ID: 4768
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic): ID: 4769
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic): ID: 4770
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol): ID: 4771
 - Yes
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife: ID: 4772
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols): ID: 4773
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans: ID: 4774
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of iconography: ID: 4775
 - No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

ID: 4776

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

ID: 4777

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

ID: 4780

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

ID: 4781

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

ID:
4782

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

ID: 4787

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

ID: 4794

– Yes

↳ Interment:

ID: 4797

– Yes

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

ID:
4808

– No

Are grave goods present:

ID: 4814

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

ID: 4815

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

ID: 4816

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

ID: 4817

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

ID: 4818

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

ID: 4819

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

ID:
4820

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

ID:
4821

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

ID: 4822

– Yes

↳ In cemetery: ID: 4823
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt: ID: 4824
– Yes
Notes: Elite families were frequently buried in elaborate tombs within burial mounds.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities): ID: 4825
– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type: ID: 4826
– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present: ID: 4827
– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present: ID: 4828
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic: ID: 4829
– Yes
Notes: Kadhi Háyuh ("Leader in the Sky")

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity: ID: 4830
– Yes
Notes: Kadhi Háyuh ("Leader in the Sky")

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld): ID: 4831

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god): ID: 4832

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god: ID: 4833

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites: ID: 4834

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites: ID: 4835

– Yes [specify]: Xinesi - a hereditary elite high priest

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good: ID: 4836

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god: ID: 4837

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world: ID: 4838

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world: ID: 4849

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward: ID: 4850

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish: ID: 4851

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world: ID: 4852
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion: ID: 4853
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion: ID: 4854
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger: ID: 4855
– No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god: ID: 4856
– No
Notes: Not as an alternative to the supreme deity.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature: ID: 4857
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living: ID: 4858
– Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life: ID: 4859
– No
 - ↳ In dreams: ID: 4860
– No

- ↳ In trance possession: ID: 4861
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices: ID: 4862
 - No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists: ID: 4863
 - Yes
 - Notes: Through the xinesi (hereditary elite high priests).
- ↳ Only through monarch ID: 4864
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living: ID: 4865
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present: ID: 4866
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can be seen: ID: 4867
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt: ID: 4868
 - Yes
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world: ID: 4869
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world: ID: 4880
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can reward: ID: 4881
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish: ID: 4882
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world: ID: 4883
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life: ID: 4884
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion: ID: 4885
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion: ID: 4886
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living: ID: 4889
 - Yes
- ↳ In waking, everyday life: ID: 4890
 - Yes
- ↳ In dreams: ID: 4891
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession: ID: 4892
 - No

- ↳ Through divination processes: ID: 4893
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through specialists: ID: 4894
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through monarch: ID: 4895
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means: ID: 4896
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present: ID: 4897
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen: ID: 4898
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt: ID: 4899
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world: ID: 4900
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world: ID: 4911
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward: ID: 4912
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish: ID: 4913
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world: ID: 4914
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion: ID: 4915
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion: ID: 4916
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger: ID: 4917
 - No

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature: ID: 4918
 - No

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings: ID: 4949
 - Yes

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model: ID: 4950
 - Yes

- ↳ Organized hierarchically: ID: 4951
 - Yes

- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific: ID: 4952
 - Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

ID:
4953

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

ID: 4954

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

ID: 4955

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

ID: 4956

– Yes

↳ Food:

ID: 4957

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

ID:
4958

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

ID:
4959

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

ID:
4960

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists: ID: 4961
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions: ID: 4962
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities: ID: 4963
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex: ID: 4964
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying: ID: 4968
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths: ID: 4969
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness: ID: 4970
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery: ID: 4971
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting: ID:
4972
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk: ID: 4973
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders: ID: 4974
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping: ID: 4975
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes: ID: 4976
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance: ID: 4977
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals: ID: 4978
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists: ID: 4979
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness: ID: 4980
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene: ID: 4981
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other: ID: 4982
– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment: ID: 4983
– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known: ID: 4984
– Yes
- ↳ Done only by high god: ID:
– No 4985
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings: ID: 4986
– Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle: ID: 4987
– No
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify] ID: 4988
– No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known: ID: 4989
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife: ID:
– No 4995
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime: ID:
– Yes 5002
- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group: ID:
– Yes 5003
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck: ID: 5004
– Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure: ID: 5005
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle: ID:
5006
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather: ID: 5007
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys. ID:
5008
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure: ID:
5009
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure: ID: 5010
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness: ID: 5011
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction: ID:
5012
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants: ID: 5013
– Yes
- ↳ Other [specify] ID: 5014
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards: ID: 5015

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known: ID: 5016

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god: ID: 5017

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings: ID: 5018

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle: ID: 5019

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence: ID: 5020

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms: ID: 5021

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness: ID: 5022

– Yes

↳ Done randomly: ID: 5023

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife: ID: 5024

– No

Notes: There was a larger emphasis on the present life.

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime: ID: 5032
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group: ID: 5033
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck: ID: 5034
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power: ID: 5035
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle: ID: 5036
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability: ID: 5037
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather: ID: 5038
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys: ID: 5039
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure: ID: 5040
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure: ID: 5041
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health: ID: 5042
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success: ID: 5043
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants: ID: 5044
– Yes

↳ Other [specify] ID: 5045
– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present: ID: 5046
– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group: ID: 5077
– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group: ID: 5078
– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence): ID: 5121
– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence): ID: 5122

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration: ID: 5127

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting: ID: 5128

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods): ID: 5129

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations: ID: 5130

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds: ID: 5131

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults: ID: 5132

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children: ID: 5137

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide): ID: 5142

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items: ID: 5143

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.): ID: 5148

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking: ID: 5149

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts: ID: 5150

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members: ID: 5151

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household): ID: 5152

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals: ID: 5154

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location: ID: 5155

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours): ID: 5156

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks: ID: 5157

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks: ID: 5158

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices: ID: 5159

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants: ID: 5160

– Yes

Notes: Heavy consumption of yaupon holly (*Ilex vomitoria* -- colloquially referred to as "black drink") until the point of vomiting and over stimulation.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present: ID: 5161

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification: ID: 5162

– Yes

- ↳ Circumcision: ID: 5163
 - No
- ↳ Food taboos: ID: 5164
 - Yes
- ↳ Hair: ID: 5165
 - Yes
- ↳ Dress: ID: 5166
 - Yes
- ↳ Ornaments: ID: 5167
 - Yes
- ↳ Archaic ritual language: ID: 5168
 - No
- ↳ Other: ID: 5169
 - No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology: ID: 5170
– Yes

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal: ID: 5171
 - Yes
- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread: ID: 5172
 - Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

ID: 5173

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

ID: 5174

– A chiefdom

Notes: While Caddo may be generally described as chiefdom during the early European Colonial period, they were part of a larger politically organized confederation that had state-like institutions and a reminder why these social organizational categories are not so clear cut.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

ID: 5175

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

ID: 5176

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

ID:

– Yes

5177

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

ID: 5178

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

ID: 5179

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5180

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents: ID: 5181

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group: ID: 5184

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group: ID: 5186

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies: ID: 5187

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage: ID: 5188

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5189

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control): ID: 5190

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5191

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure: ID: 5192

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance of common routes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5193

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes: ID: 5194

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5195

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force: ID: 5196

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5197

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

ID: 5198

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

ID: 5199

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

ID:
5200

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

ID:
5201

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

ID: 5202

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

ID: 5203

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

ID: 5204

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

ID:
5205

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

ID: 5206

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code: ID: 5212

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5213

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military: ID: 5214

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript: ID: 5215

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard): ID: 5216

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army: ID: 5217

– Yes

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5218

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5219

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language: ID: 5220

– Yes

Notes: A written script was introduced in recent history.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5222

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5223

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar: ID: 5224

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5225

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves: ID: 5226

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]: ID: 5227

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5228

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Caddo, Bolton, Herbert. *The Hasinai: Southern Caddoans as Seen by the Earliest Europeans*. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 2002.

Reference: Caddo, Brown, James, Alice Brues, Lyle Konigsberg, Paul Parmalee, and David Stansbery. *The Spiro Ceremonial Center: The Archaeology of Arkansas Valley Caddoan Culture in Eastern Oklahoma*. Vol. 1–2. Ann Arbor: Museum of Anthropology, University of Michigan, 1996.

Reference: Caddo, Carter, Cecile. *Caddo Indians: Where We Come from*. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 2001.

Reference: Caddo, Emerson, Thomas, and Jeffrey Girard. "Dating Gahagan and Its Implications for Understanding Cahokia-caddo Interactions". *Southeastern Archaeology* 23, no. 1 (2004): 57–64.

Reference: Caddo, LaVere, David. *The Caddo Chiefdoms: Caddo Economics and Politics, 700-1835*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1998.

Reference: Caddo, McKinnon, Duncan. "Exploring Settlement Patterning at a Premiere Caddo Mound Site in the Red River Great Bend Region". *Southeastern Archaeology* 28, no. 2 (2009): 248–58.

Reference: Caddo, Perttula, Timothy. *The Caddo Nation: Archaeological and Ethnohistoric Perspectives*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1997.

Reference: Caddo, Phillips, Philip, and James Brown. *Pre-columbian Shell Engravings from the Craig Mound at Spiro, Oklahoma*. Cambridge: Peabody Museum Press, 1984.

Reference: Caddo, Smith, F. Todd. *The Caddo Indians: Tribes at the Convergence of Empires, 1542-1854*. College Station: Texas A&M Press, 1995.

Reference: Caddo, Watkins, Joe. "Artefactual Awareness: Spiro Mounds, Grave Goods and Politics". In *The Dead and Their Possessions: Repatriation in Principle, Policy and Practice*, edited by Cressida Fforde, Jane Hubert, and Paul Turnbull, 149–59. London: Routledge, n.d..

Reference: Caddo, Caddo Nation. "Caddo Nation Website: Who We Are", 2023.

<https://mycaddonation.com/history-1>.

Reference: Caddo, National Park Service. "NPS Website: Early Caddo History - El Camino Real De Los Tejas", 2025. <https://www.nps.gov/elte/learn/historyculture/caddo-early-history.htm>.